
Easy Multiplication Using Grid

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Summary— This educational innovation addresses the challenges students face in understanding multiplication by introducing a visual aid called the Multiplication Grid. Research shows that difficulties in grasping basic mathematical concepts like multiplication persist among many students, impacting their overall academic performance. The Multiplication Grid provides a structured and visual method to help students internalize multiplication concepts by breaking down the process into manageable steps. This approach aligns with the Department of Education's goals of enhancing teaching methods and making learning more accessible and effective for all students. The grid helps students visualize and understand multiplication operations by using tally marks and patterns, thus reducing confusion and promoting a deeper understanding of the subject. The implementation involves a systematic process where students' needs are assessed, appropriate activities are assigned, and continuous support is provided to ensure comprehension and progress. This method has proven to improve students' multiplication skills, leading to increased confidence and academic achievement.

Keywords— Instructional Strategies, Mathematics Education, Multiplication, Visual Learning

I. OVERVIEW

The primary challenge in providing basic education lies in students' difficulties with fundamental concepts like multiplication. Research by Igarashi and Suryadarma (2023) indicates that as many as one in every ten tenth-grade students still struggle to solve multiplication problems. Addressing such challenges positively influences the education system as student knowledge and understanding of core concepts improves, the teachers acquire effective instruction methods, and students' academic achievements increase. The innovation of using a grid directly addresses the challenges in that it provides a visual and structured form of understanding multiplication which can help unravel the concepts and diminish confusion thereby further providing a conducive platform for students to have a basic grasp of multiplication.

This innovation aligns with the Department of Education's goals of providing quality education by ensuring teachers use effective teaching methods that engage students in math, cater to diverse learning needs, and enhance educational practices overall. Hence, the innovation embodies the Department of Education's core values, focusing on inclusivity, accessibility, and effective education.

II. INNOVATION DESCRIPTION

The innovation involves utilizing grids as a visual aid to help students grasp multiplication concepts. It features structured grids resembling multiplication tables, with numerical elements displayed above as multiplicands and corresponding boxes below where students can represent their answers using tally marks to count. Its functionalities include using the grid to illustrate multiplication operations, highlight patterns, and simplify comprehension of multiplication principles. Innovation functions by providing a real and visual manifestation of the process of multiplication hence making it easier to understand. The idea of multiplication concepts is demonstrated in a structured grid format showing the relationship between numbers as well as the visual process of multiplication, thus clearing the confusion and letting students understand better.

The innovation is much better compared to other solutions because it gives a tangible visual tool that is suitable for learners who are having difficulty learning multiplication tables and it is accessible for them to use inside the classroom. Utilizing the visual representation of multiplication through grids taps into our innate capacity to process visual information effectively. Booyesen and Westaway (2022) highlight the importance of visual representations as crucial tools for learners to develop a deeper understanding of multiplication concepts.

To demonstrate the process of the innovation, let's explore how to utilize the Multiplication Grid. When a student encounters a problem like $5 \times 3 = n$, they first write the multiplier in the designated blank space. Following this, within the yellow box, learners depict tally marks corresponding to

the multiplication. Finally, they write down the final figure in the green box, aiding in a clear understanding and accurate derivation of the correct answer.

III. INNOVATION STATEMENT

The innovation's main aim and target is centered on improving Grade Three learners' understanding and internalization of multiplication concepts within the educational framework. The approach utilized is Multiplication Grid which is intended to give students a visual and structured means of understanding multiplication and thus solve the difficulties associated with the traditional teaching methods. The innovation seeks to create learner-centered conditions by considering individual's learning styles and encouraging the involvement and active participation of students in mathematics instruction. Innovation is achieved using visual representations and hands-on activities, which promote deep understanding, identification of patterns, and solution of multiplication problems, bringing about the students' confidence.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE

a. Process Flow Framework

The process flow or framework of the innovation begins with identifying the learners' needs, primarily through assessments. Following this, learners are organized based on their abilities. Those who demonstrate proficiency are provided with leveled activities tailored to their skill level, while those encountering challenges are given the Multiplication Grid. Subsequently, they are guided through a three-step process on how to effectively utilize the provided resources. To ensure comprehension, learners' understanding is assessed, and additional support is offered to address any confusion or uncertainties. Those requiring further assistance engage in guided activities, whereas those showing progress are encouraged to undertake independent practice to reinforce their newly acquired skills.

The steps are interconnected and sequentially build upon each other, facilitating a smooth and efficient operation of the innovation process. By following a structured and methodical order, each step informs and influences the next, ensuring a cohesive progression toward the goal. This approach enables effective coordination, minimizes disruptions, and maximizes the effectiveness of the innovation implementation, leading to improved outcomes and greater success in achieving the desired objectives.

The method used in the innovation employing the Multiplication Grid involves visual and hands-on learning. By using the grid, pupils learn to apply a visual and touch-based approach to concrete multiplication concepts. The teacher uses a grid to visualize multiplication operations, spot the patterns, and come across the solutions of the multiplication problems, thereby improving their understanding and knowledge of the multiplication theories. The approach is based on human visual information processing competence, thus enabling learners with different styles of learning to connect with the learning process better.

b. Project Management

The innovation was managed by ensuring that all students in the class had access to the necessary materials so that everyone could utilize them if desired. The materials used in its development were made readily accessible to facilitate ease of use and implementation.

Project management strategies employed to ensure the successful execution of the innovation include establishing clear goals and objectives, creating detailed timelines and milestones, allocating resources effectively, and conducting regular progress reviews and evaluations. These strategies help to streamline processes, mitigate risks, and ensure that the innovation stays on track to achieve its intended outcomes.

The key stakeholders involved in managing and implementing the innovation are the teachers and learners. Teachers ensure that learners utilize the innovation materials and observe progress and improvements during implementation. Learners play a crucial role in providing feedback to ensure that the materials being used effectively meet their learning needs and help them achieve their educational goals.

c. Timeline

The implementation timeline for this innovation was set for the beginning of the second quarter, following the identification of learning difficulties among specific students during multiplication lessons in the first week.

During the implementation stage, the process began by individually calling students to answer multiplication facts. Those who encountered difficulty were assisted using an improvised grid made of masking tape and small pebbles. However, as the need for a more accessible and independent tool arose, this led to the development of the Multiplication Grid. The modification was driven by the aim to enhance accessibility for learners, enabling them to use the material at their desks without constant teacher guidance or even take it home for further practice.

In the post-implementation phase, the innovation was showcased during LAC Sessions to demonstrate an example of innovative teaching material to teachers. Additionally, Action Research was conducted to assess its effectiveness and gather data to support its efficacy. Based on this evaluation, refinements may be made to the innovation, including adjustments to the materials used, modifications to implementation strategies, or enhancements to support mechanisms. Furthermore, opportunities for potential expansion of the innovation may arise to reach more students or address additional learning needs. This expansion could involve adapting the innovation to different educational contexts or subject areas. Through ongoing evaluation, refinement, and potential expansion, the innovation continues to evolve and adapt to better meet the needs of both learners and educators.

d. Resource Utilization

The primary resources utilized in this innovation include a laptop for designing the multiplication grid, bond paper, a printer, and whiteboard markers. To ensure reusability, teachers can opt to laminate the grids or utilize certificate holders to insert printed multiplication grids, allowing them

Fig. 1: Multiplication Grid

Fig. 2: Process Flow

to write on the surface using markers.

By employing lamination or certificate holders, the multiplication grid can be utilized repeatedly, enhancing its longevity and sustainability. Initially, during the development phase, some iterations and adjustments necessitated reprinting. However, once the final design was achieved, subsequent printing became unnecessary, ensuring efficiency in

resource utilization.

To achieve cost-effectiveness and sustainability, the teacher repurposed certificate holders received from training sessions and utilized refillable whiteboard markers with existing whiteboards. This approach minimized expenditure as the materials were readily available, contributing to efficient resource utilization.

e. Progress Monitoring

The teacher is responsible for monitoring the progress and outcomes of the innovation's implementation to ensure it fulfills its purpose of improving students' multiplication skills. This involves recording learners' activity scores, observing their behaviors, and gathering feedback on the innovation's utilization to assess its effectiveness.

The teacher maintains a record sheet to document learners' scores, observations, and feedback. This record sheet serves as a valuable tool for tracking student progress, noting any notable observations or behaviors, and collecting feedback on the effectiveness of the innovation's implementation. It provides a comprehensive overview of how the innovation is impacting students' multiplication skills and guides future adjustments or refinements to optimize learning outcomes. The teacher utilizes daily activity assessment and observation record sheets to monitor progress, aiding in informed decision-making processes.

V. SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

I intend to consistently incorporate the Multiplication Grid into my teaching practices by reintroducing it to my students each year. This ensures that more students have the opportunity to benefit from its use. Additionally, I will store the grids in an accessible location to ensure they are readily available for use when needed. By reintroducing the innovation yearly and keeping it accessible, there is a consistent provision of support for students' multiplication skills. This reduces the risk of discontinuity in the use of the innovation and helps maintain its effectiveness over time.

This may involve incorporating feedback from teachers and students to make necessary improvements, such as refining the design of the grid or adding supplementary resources to enhance learning experiences. Collaboration with educational experts and researchers can provide insights into innovative teaching methodologies and instructional practices to continuously enhance innovation. The innovation may lead to a more inclusive learning environment where students of diverse learning styles and abilities can thrive, ultimately contributing to broader academic success and achievement.

Outputs/Outcomes (Enumerates the outputs or outcomes produced from this innovation	Beneficiary/ies (who benefited from the corresponding results or outcomes
By using the motivation learners were able to answer independently multiplication facts.	The beneficiaries are the three Grade 3 learners who are struggling with multiplication.

Fig. 3: Innovation Output/Outcomes

REFERENCES

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